

Remediation of paddy soil contaminated by endosulfan residues by applying a combination of farmyard manures and corn cob biochar

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ABSTRACT

Organochlorine insecticides including endosulfan are used intensively since Indonesia's 'green revolution' of the 1960s to 1980s, to reduce yield loss of food crops due to pest incidence. As one of the persistent organic pollutants (POPs) compounds, endosulfan residues are still found in rice fields to the present day although it had already banned. Using organic matter such as biochar and farmyard manures is a remediation strategy to reduce endosulfan concentration in soils. This research was conducted in a greenhouse to determine the concentration of endosulfan residues in paddy soils which applied a combination of farmyard manures and corn cob biochar. The experiment was conducted with a completely randomized design including three replicates and seven treatments that combined farmyard manures and corn cob biochar. The 14-days old seedling of Ciherang variety was transplanted into pots weighing 13 kg with paddy soils. Variables measured were grain yield, yield component, crop agronomic growth, endosulfan concentration in soil, water, grains, microbial population, soil pH, and redox potential. The combination of cattle farmyard manure and biochar with a 4:1 ratio reduced effectively the largest endosulfan residues in the panicle initiation growth phase and maturity growth phase by as much as 68.1% and 62.8%, respectively, compared with treatment of without soil amendment. The largest microbial population in the panicle initiation growth phase was achieved by a treatment that combined cattle farmyard manure and biochar with a 4:1 ratio. The combination of farmyard manure and corn cob biochar reduced a significant amount of endosulfan in percolation water and rice grains. As well as functioning as a remediator, organic soil amendment which consists of farmyard manure and corn cob biochar improves rice productivity significantly by as much as 8–26%.

Key words: biochar, farmyard manure, endosulfan residue, grain yield

INTRODUCTION

Insecticide plays a role in increasing crop productivity such as controlling harmful pests. The intensive use of insecticides for food crops increased sharply during the 'green revolution' of the 1960s that many countries engaged in (Popp et al. 2013), including Indonesia. The government program of providing subsidies of at least 80% enabled farmers to obtain easily available

chemical fertilizers and pesticides. One such pesticide which was used intensively by farmers as an insecticide was endosulfan which is characterized as having active ingredients. Its toxic properties led to this insecticide being prohibited from food crop cultivation since the 1980s, when the government released Presidential Instruction No. 3/1986. However, some formulations with active ingredients like that appearing in endosulfan are found in agricultural fields.

Endosulfan (*6,7,8,9,10,10-hexachloro-1,5,5a,6,9,9a-hexahydro-6,9-methano-2,4,3-benzodioxathiepine-3-oxide*) is an organochlorine insecticides that is still detected on farming lands. Endosulfan belongs to the cyclodiene family of compounds and acts to kill a wide variety of insects (Thangadurai & Suresh 2014). Endosulfan is hydrophilic with a mass of 406,939 per mole, density of 1.745 g/cm³, melting point of 70-100 °C, and solubility in water of 0.33 mg/L. Endosulfan consists of two isomers, namely α -endosulfan and β -endosulfan that could be degraded into sulphate endosulfan and endosulfan diol (Weber et al. 2010). Endosulfan exposure can cause acute and chronic risks to non-targets such as birds, fish, livestock, and humans. Pesticides that are highly toxic (LC50) are more poisonous to organisms (Taylor et al. 2003). Human exposure to endosulfan can cause liver and kidney damage, nervous disorders, reproduction and developmental problems (Houlihan et al. 2000; Thangadurai & Suresh 2014).

Endosulfan includes twelve compounds derived from persistent organic pollutants (POPs) which were determined by the Stockholm Convention that came into effect in 2004 (Li et al. 2011). As one of the POPs, endosulfan and other organochlorine pesticides are relatively difficult to degrade and their residues can accumulate in soil, water, and agricultural products (Falahudin & Munawir 2012). Endosulfan accumulation in soil, water, and products will seriously endanger the environment and human health. People's health is disrupted by indirect interaction between POPs content in soil and the atmosphere, biosphere, and hydrosphere (Li et al. 2011). The POPs' fate and distribution in rice fields is influenced by condition of soil moisture fluctuation, and the photolysis and volatilization processes in soil. Dissipation of organic contaminants depends on soil particles' binding and processes of photolysis, hydrolysis, and volatilization (Roche et al. 2009).

In Indonesia, endosulfan still exists on agricultural lands with a concentration of 5-13 ppb on land set aside for the cultivation of vegetables, and in the 15.7-97 ppb range on rice fields. As much as 219.6 ppb concentration of endosulfan has been detected in rice fields in the downstream Brantas catchment area, and as much as 680 ppb in vegetable-growing land has been detected in the upstream Citarum catchment area (Ardiwinata et al. 1997; Ramadhani & Oginawati 2009). Residues of endosulfan were also found in fish (0.48-15.54 ppb) in the Citarum catchment area (Paramita & Oginawati 2009), in

which is a major rice-growing region of Central Java (Ardiwinata&Nursyamsi 2012). Furthermore 3.6-13.4 ppb was found in salad vegetables in Cianjur, West Java (Miskiyah&Munarso 2009). According to Alberta Environment Canada (2009), the maximum limit of endosulfan residue in soils should be 8.5 ppb.

Remediation of agricultural soils polluted by pesticide residues can be controlled by using agricultural wastes and farmyard manures which serve as adsorption agents. Agricultural wastes in surrounding rice fields are available abundant such as rice husks, nut shell beans, corn cobs, corn stalks, sorghum stalks, coconut shell, and palm bunches. In Indonesia, waste of corn cob is very abundant and this linked to maize production, and in 2014 as much as 19.033.000 tons during 2015-2019. During this period the focus was ensuring the maize production was as self-sufficient as possible (Ministry of Agriculture 2015). Apart from being composted, agricultural wastes with high levels of lignin can be used as materials for bio-charcoal or biochar through the process of pyrolysis without oxygen (Glaser et al. 2002). Biochar has a role to play in making sustainable agriculture, by increasing the available nutrients, retention of water and nutrients (Nuridaet al. 2013), habitat of microorganisms (Ogawa 1994), food crop productivity (Jones et al. 2012), carbon sequestration in soils (Ogawa et al. 2006), and reduction of pesticides in soil (Hammes& Schmidt 2009). Application of 0.4-8 tons biochar per hectare can enhance crop productivity by as much as 20-220% based on the type of commodity (Gani 2009). Biochar has many pores that provide an ideal microbial habitat (Santi&Goenadi 2010), including the potential of microbes to degrade pesticide residues in soils.

Farmers had used manure in their farming systems previously before the green revolution. Farmyard manures (FYM) are used to improve the soils' physical, chemical and biological properties, increase fertilizer use efficiency, and control the pollution problem (Wolf & Snyder 2003). Animal manure contains 40-60% C on a dry weight basis, and its application to land should promote soil organic carbon sequestration and enhance microbial functions (Johnson et al. 2007). According to Soejitno (2006), soil that is high in organic matter can adsorb more pesticide residues compared to soil with little organic matter. The objective of this research was to determine the content of endosulfan residue in soil and rice grains. It did this through remediation using a combination of farmyard manures and biochar of corn cobs in paddy soils from Jombang, East Java.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location and time of research

This research was the second rice cropping season that continued the first cropping season, the objective being to remediate paddy soil contaminated by endosulfan residue. The experiment was carried out in a greenhouse operated by the Indonesian Agricultural Environment Research Institute at Jakenan, Pati District, province of Central Java during November 2015 to April 2016. The experiment was conducted at the precise location of 6°46'29.8" S and 111°11'51.5" E with an elevation of 34 m above sea level. Sample of soil contaminated endosulfan residue was taken in rice field at Plandi, Jombang subdistrict, East Java.

Experimental design

The greenhouse experiment was arranged using a completely randomized design with three replicates and seven treatments. The seven treatments were as follows:

A0 =	Without applying soil amendment as control
A1 =	Combination between farmyard manure of chicken and corn cob biochar with 4:1 ratio
A2 =	Combination between farmyard manure of chicken and corn cob biochar with 4:2 ratio
A3 =	Combination between farmyard manure of chicken and corn cob biochar with 1:1 ratio
A4 =	Combination between farmyard manure of cattle and corn cob biochar with 4:1 ratio
A5 =	Combination between farmyard manure of cattle and corn cob biochar with 4:2 ratio
A6 =	Combination between farmyard manure of cattle and corn cob biochar with 1:1 ratio

The ratio for corn cob biochar to farmyard manure was based on research results documented by Nurida et al. (2013). Specifically, it was 1:4 and 2:4 by dry weight. Manure from cattle and chicken served as the composted farmyard manure with C/N ratio = 20.

Procedures of greenhouse experiment

The composite soil samples from rice field contaminated endosulfan residue were air-dried, ground and passed through a 2 mm sieve. The chemical property of initial soil sample was pH-H₂O 5.91±0.16, pH-KCl 5.67±0.11, low organic C (0.88±0.04%), moderate cation exchange capacity (13.79±4.98 cmol/kg), high exchangeable cations (K, Na, Ca, Mg with values of 0.63, 4.62, 24.34, 3.55 cmol/kg, respectively), low exchangeable aluminum (0.51±0.14 cmol/kg), low exchangeable H (0.53±0.18 cmol/kg), P extracted by 25% HCl (3.84 g P₂O₅/kg), and K extracted by 25% HCl (0.34 g K₂O/kg). The soil samples were predominantly clay fraction or clay textural class consisting of 23.13% sand,

8.89% silt, and 57.98% clay. The concentration of endosulfan in soil sample was 0.16 ppm and this was more than the maximum residue limit (0.0085 ppm).

A soil sample was put into each PVC pot (26 cm in diameter) that was 13 kg by dry weight. Each pot had a soil amendment applied to it, and this was a combination of farmyard manure and biochar. The dosage was 2 ton/ha which fit the treatments' formulation. Soil amendment was incorporated into the soil (Zhang et al. 2010) and mixed homogenously, and incubated for one week. The pot's soil moisture content was maintained in a submerged state during the rice growth phase using a water-free contaminant whose concentration was less than 0.0021 ppm (limit of detection for POPs compounds).

Two seedlings of the Ciherang rice variety were transplanted into each pot two weeks after germination. The recommended fertilizer rates for N, P, K were 138 kg N, 27 kg P₂O₅, and 60 kg K₂O per hectare, respectively, which was a specific fit for rice fields of Jombang. The N fertilizer was applied to three stages, namely 1/3N before transplanting time, 1/3N at active tillering growth stage, and 1/3N at panicle initiation growth stage. The P fertilizer was applied once before transplanting time. The K fertilizer was applied twice, namely 1/2K before transplantation and 1/2K at panicle initiation. The crop was intensively maintained throughout this process.

Variables observed comprised crop agronomic growth, potential grain yield, yield component, concentration of endosulfan residue in soil, percolation water, grains, soil pH, redox potential, microbial population. The microbial population was determined using the MPN method during the panicle initiation growth phase. Variables of agronomic growth, i.e. plant height, number of productive tillers, yield component and potential grain yield were measured using the IRRM method. The concentration of endosulfan residue in soil and percolation water was analyzed 7 days after applying soil amendment, the panicle initiation growth phase, and prior to harvesting. Determination of endosulfan residue in product references guide of analysis on pesticide residue published by Pesticide Commission (1997). The concentration of endosulfan in soil and product was determined using gas liquid chromatography according to the standard method SNI 06-6991.1-2004 and Pesticide Commission (1997), while SNI 06-6990.1-2004 determines the amount of endosulfan in water.

Concentrations of endosulfan residue in samples of soil, water, and crops were calculated using the equation as advised by the Pesticide Commission (1997) as follows:

$$\text{Residue} = \frac{A_c \times V_{is} \times K_s \times V_{fc}}{A_s \times V_{ic} \times B \times R}$$

Note:

Residue = in ppm

Ac = area of sample

As = area of standard

Vic = volume of sample injection (μL)

Vis = volume of standard injection (μL)

Ks = concentration of standard (ppm)

B = early weight or volume (mg or ml)

R = recovery (%)

Data analysis

The data collected was investigated statistically with analysis of variance using the SAS program software. This was then continued with Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at 5% to determine the significant differences among treatments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Endosulfan residue in soils

High residues of organochlorine pesticides, including endosulfa were detected in rice paddy soils in some areas of Jombang district. The concentration of endosulfan residue in soil before remediation was 0.16 ppm, and this concentration was over the maximum residue limit (MRL) in soil, i.e. 0.0085 ppm. After harvesting the rice during the first cropping season, the concentration of endosulfan residue in soil without applying soil amendment is 0.0182 ppm, whereas of the treatment that combined farmyard manure and corn cob biochar ranged from 0.0053–0.0089 ppm (Figure 1).

Following remediation, applying only soil organic amendment significantly reduced endosulfan concentration in soil before harvesting time ($p = 0.056$). Concentrations of endosulfan residue after applying soil amendment consisting of farmyard manure combined with biochar on panicle initiation and maturity growth phases were, 0.0021–0.0053 and 0.0032–0.0068 ppm, respectively. Furthermore the concentrations of endosulfan residue when treated without soil amendment were 0.0067 and 0.0087 ppm, also respectively. The concentration of residue after applying soil amendment was generally lower than the recommended MRL in soil (i.e. 0.0085 ppm).

The smaller concentration of residue after remediation was achieved by treatment that combined cattle manure and corn cob biochar with a 4:1 ratio, especially during the panicle initiation and maturity growth phases (Figure 1). Treatment of cattle manure combined with biochar at the ratio of 4:1 effectively reduced the highest endosulfan residue during both panicle initiation and maturity growth phases as much as 68.1% and 62.8%, respectively. This was very comparable to the treatment without soil amendment (control).

Figure 1. Dynamic of endosulfan residue in paddy soil treated with various combination between farmyard manure and biochar, 2015-2016 (T1 = before remediation, T2 = 7 days after applying soil amendment, T3 = panicle initiation growth phase, T4 = maturity phase or before harvesting time; A0 = without applying soil amendment, A1 = Remediation with chicken manure and biochar in 4:1 ratio, A2 = Remediation with chicken manure and biochar in 4:2 ratio, A3 = Remediation with chicken manure and biochar in 1:1 ratio, A4 = Remediation with cattle manure and biochar in 4:1 ratio, A5 = Remediation with cattle manure and biochar in 4:2 ratio, A6 = Remediation with cattle manure and biochar in 1:1 ratio)

Application of farmyard manure combined with biochar generally reduced the amount of endosulfan residue existing in paddy soils. An organic amendment such as composted animal manure and biochar provided some functional groups (carboxyl, phenolic, hydroxyl) that adsorb endosulfan compounds within their surfaces (Hammes & Schmidt 2009). Referring to the maturity growth phase, the concentration of endosulfan residue in soil was larger than during the panicle initiation growth phase, despite its concentration being smaller than the MRL. The high residue concentration is attributed by the release of endosulfan compounds which bind weakly to the surface of soil particles and organic materials in the rhizosphere. According to Handayanto and Hairiah (2007), the rhizosphere of rice crop bacteria have the potential to degrade residue pesticides, and this property is evident in such bacteria as *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* and *Bacillus sp.*

Reducing endosulfan residues in soil is possible using all treatments, including the control or without applying a soil amendment. This reduction is caused by strong adsorption by clay and microbial degradation. In the rhizosphere of rice crops, several microbes can use root exudates as an energy

source, including microbes that can potentially degrade pesticide residue. The existence of microbes in the rhizosphere can also reduce endosulfan residue where treatment does not involve soil amendment.

The amount of endosulfan in rice paddy soil significantly affects the existence of bacteria in the regions surrounding the rice roots. Most bacteria and fungi are capable of utilizing endosulfan as a sole source of carbon and/or sulfur. Concentration of endosulfan residue in soil correlates negatively and significantly with the total bacteria and fungipopulation. The significant relationship is confirmed by $p = 0.0001$ for total bacteria and $p = 0.006$ for fungi (Figure 2). The high amount of bacteria and fungi in the rhizosphere uces significantly reduces endosulfan residue in paddy soils as demonstrated by thelinear equation $Re = -0.00003 B + 0.0106$ ($R^2 = 0.4982$, $n = 21$) for bacteria and $Re = -0.0001 F + 0.0071$ ($R^2 = 0.335$, $n = 21$) for fungi. In this context the following apply: Re = concentration of endosulfan residue in soil; B = population of total bacteria in soil; and F = population of fungi in soil (Figure 2). Some bacteria that have the potential to degrade pesticide residue exist in the rice crop's rhizosphere, i.e. *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* (Thangadurai& Suresh 2014) and *Bacillus sp.*

Application of farmyard manure and biochar to soil generally increases the population of total bacteria and fungi (Table 1). Farmyard manure and biochar provide organic materials which use microbes as an energy source to support their activity in degrading pesticide residues. One such bacteria that can degrade organochlorine is *Bacillus sp.* Having a large population of total bacteria and fungi in rice paddy soils is evident in the treatment when cattle manure and corn cob biochar are combined at a 4:1 ratio (A4) (Table 1). The microbial population generally is higher if the farmyard manure from cattle, rather than chicken manure,is mixed with biochar.

General of *Bacillus sp* is one type of bacteria that is capable of degrading pesticide compounds in soil. Harsantiet al. (2013) reported that the application of active charcoal derived from corn cob increased microbial population in the soil (range of 109-1010colony-forming unit per g soil) compared with active charcoal originating from other agricultural wastes (range of 108-109 colony-forming unit per g soil). Some bacteria that can degrade pesticide residuesare *Citrobacter sp*, *Enterobacter sp*, *Azotobacter sp*, and *Bacillus sp*. According toTaylor et al. (2003), some bacteria that can also degrade endosulfan in soil are *Klebsiella*, *Acinetobacter*, *Alcaligenes*, *Bacillus*, and *Flavobacterium*. Table 1 shows that the highest population of Bacillusspw as achieved when treatment involved a combination of: firstly, farmyard chicken manure ken and corn cob biochar at the ratio of 1:1 (A3); and secondly, farmyard cattle manure and corn cob biochar at a ratio of 4:1 (A4).

Figure 2. Relationship between concentration of endosulfan residue and microbe in soil at panicle initiation growth phase

Table 1. Population of bacteria and fungi in paddy soils at panicle initiation phase of Ciherang variety on various treatments of farmyard manure combined with biochar, 2015-2016

Treatment	Bacteria* (10 ⁵ CFU/g soil)	<i>Bacillus</i> sp* (10 ³ CFU/g soil)	Fungi* (10 ⁴ CFU/g soil)
A0 = without applying soil amendment	8.5	1	0
A1 = Remediation with chicken manure and biochar in 4:1 ratio	10.5	5	0
A2 = Remediation with chicken manure and biochar in 4:2 ratio	19	2	0.5
A3 = Remediation with chicken manure and biochar in 1:1 ratio	13.5	13	0.5
A4 = Remediation with cattle manure and biochar in 4:1 ratio	30.5	13	4
A5 = Remediation with cattle manure and biochar in 4:2 ratio	23	2	1
A6 = Remediation with cattle manure and biochar in 1:1 ratio	21.5	2	1

* Average from three replicates, CFU = colony forming unit

Endosulfan residue in percolation water

Concentration of endosulfan in percolation water tends to decrease during the panicle initiation and maturity growth phases. Furthermore its concentration is extremely small (less than 0.006 ppm) in all treatments either with or without soil amendment (Figure 3). Application of combined farmyard manure and biochar significantly reduces endosulfan content in percolation water.

Figure 3. Dynamics of endosulfan residue in percolation water treated with various combinations of farmyard manure and biochar, 2015-2016 (T2 = 7 days after applying soil amendment, T3 = panicle initiation growth phase, T4 = maturity phase or before harvesting time; A0 = without applying soil amendment, A1 = Remediation with chicken manure and biochar at a 4:1 ratio, A2 = Remediation with chicken manure and biochar at a 4:2 ratio, A3 = Remediation with chicken manure and biochar at a 1:1 ratio, A4 = Remediation with cattle manure and biochar at a 4:1 ratio, A5 = Remediation with cattle manure and biochar at a 4:2 ratio, A6 = Remediation with cattle manure and biochar at a 1:1 ratio)

The existence of insecticide compounds in paddy soil and water is affected by adsorption capacity of soil particles, soil organic matter content, organic material input, soil property, and soil moisture content. Application of organic matter to submerged rice paddy soils might reduce soil acidity and increase the surface negative charge of soil particles, enabling it to retain or adsorb insecticide compounds. As the rice crop grows, the soil always remains in a submerged state and existing endosulfan residue in water tends to decline during the maturity growth phase. Endosulfan that is bound weakly on soil particles will be released into soil solution and percolation water, so that the dissolved endosulfan concentration will increase. However, adding farmyard manure combined with biochar can reduce dissolved endosulfan in water. This results in the maturity phase concentration becoming relatively small. This finding is similar with what was reported by Chou and Chiou (1997). They found that the lowest concentration of volatile organic compounds occurred in the highest moisture content in soil.

Endosulfan residue in rice grains

The concentration of endosulfan in rice grains is smaller if farmyard chicken manure is applied instead of cattle manure. As presented in Table 2

below, the concentration of endosulfan residue in grains when utilizing all treatments is generally lower than the MRL (0.1 ppm). The highest concentration is shown when treatment is a combination of cattle manure and corn cob biochar at a ratio of 4:2 (A5), followed by treatment without soil amendment or control (A0). This seems to suggest that the low endosulfan concentration in soil treated with chicken manure is due to more endosulfan being taken up by the rice crop and becomes translocated into the grains.

Table 2. Endosulfan residue in rice grains from various treatments of farmyard manures combined with biochar, 2015-2016

Treatment	Endosulfan concentration in grains (ppm)
A0 = without applying soil amendment	0.0347 ab
A1 = Remediation with chicken manure and biochar in 4:1 ratio	0.0250 b
A2 = Remediation with chicken manure and biochar in 4:2 ratio	0.0223 b
A3 = Remediation with chicken manure and biochar in 1:1 ratio	0.0254 b
A4 = Remediation with cattle manure and biochar in 4:1 ratio	0.0342 ab
A5 = Remediation with cattle manure and biochar in 4:2 ratio	0.0384 a
A6 = Remediation with cattle manure and biochar in 1:1 ratio	0.0274 ab
MRLs of endosulfan	0.1000
P < Fr	0.0675
Coefficient of variance (%)	22.0752

Mean in same column followed by same letter is not different significantly according DMRT 5%

Application of farmyard manure and biochar reduces endosulfan compounds in soil and subsequently the endosulfan uptake will be low. The reduction of endosulfan in grains is attributed to weak retention between the endosulfan compound and clay surface, adsorption on biochar and organic material derived from farmyard manure through van der Waals forces and hydrogen bindings (Hammes & Schmidt 2009). The small amount of dissolved endosulfan in soil decreases the translocation of endosulfan compounds into the rice crop. Furthermore the concentration of endosulfan residue in rice grains is smaller than 0.04 ppm (Table 2). Endosulfan absorbed in grains is lower than the MRL (0.1 ppm). Although rice grains contain only small amounts of endosulfan, its long-term accumulation in tissue can harm human health because endosulfan is a POPs compound with toxic and persistent characteristics.

Grain yield and growth of Ciherang

Application of farmyard manure combined with corn cob biochar does not significantly affect crop growth, especially plant height and maximum number of tillers. However, it will significantly influence the number of productive tillers ($p = 0.0029$) as presented in Table 3. The plant height of the

Ciherang variety ranges from 93-98 cm. Number of maximum and productive tillers ranges from 25-29 tillers per hill and 22-26 tillers per hill, respectively. The number of productive tillers that use a treatment combining farmyard manure and biochar is higher than without soil amendment.

Table 3. Rice growth on various treatments of farmyard manures combined with corn cob biochar

Treatments	Plant height at harvesting time (cm)	Tiller number per hill	
		Maximum	Productive
A0	93.0 a	25.2 a	22.5 d
A1	94.9 a	27.0 a	23.5 cd
A2	94.0 a	27.5 a	25.7 a
A3	97.6 a	28.7 a	25.3 ab
A4	94.4 a	27.5 a	24.5 abc
A5	95.2 a	26.7 a	24.0 bc
A6	95.9 a	27.3 a	25.2 ab
P > Fr	0.5736	0.5276	0.0029
Coefficient of variance (%)	2.9704	7.1859	3.2885

Mean in same column followed by same letter is not different significantly according to DMRT (5%)

A0 = without applying soil amendment (control), A1= Combination of chicken manure and corn cob biochar at a 4:1 ratio, A2 = Combination of chicken manure and corn cob biochar at a 4:2 ratio, A3 = Combination of chicken manure and corn cob biochar at a 1:1 ratio, A4 = Combination of cattle manure and corn cob biochar at a 4:1 ratio, A5 = Combination of cattle manure and corn cob biochar at a 4:2 ratio, A6 = Combination of cattle manure and corn cob biochar at a 1:1 ratio

Yield component of the Ciherang variety is not affected by applying a combination of farmyard manure and biochar, except weight of 1000-grains ($p < 0.05$) (Table 4). Grain yield is affected significantly by the application of organic amendment in soil ($p < 0.01$). Application of farmyard manure combined with biochar generally increases crop productivity by as much as 8–26%. The highest grain yield was achieved by treatment where chicken manure and corn cob biochar were combined at a ratio of 1:1 (A6).

Table 4. Yield component and grain yield of Ciherang variety on various treatments of farmyard manures combined with corn cob biochar

Treatments	Number of total grains per panicle	% of filled grains per panicle	Weight of 1000-grains (g)	Potential grain yield	
				g/pot	kg/ha
A0	113.0 a	87.1 a	22.83 b	50.64 c	9509 c
A1	117.9 a	84.4 a	23.44 ab	54.92 bc	10349 bc
A2	116.5 a	87.7 a	23.07 b	60.54 ab	11409 ab
A3	119.2 a	88.4 a	23.96 a	63.68 a	12000 a
A4	111.7 a	89.6 a	23.40 ab	57.29 b	10796 b
A5	118.0 a	87.0 a	23.30 ab	57.36 b	10809 b
A6	113.0 a	86.4 a	23.04 b	56.52 bc	10651 bc
P > Fr	0.4336	0.9097	0.0492	0.0086	0.0086
Coefficient of variance (%)	4.3358	5.5709	1.6058	5.8657	5.8645

Mean in same column followed by same letter is not different significantly according to DMRT (5%)

A0 = without applying soil amendment (control), A1= Combination of chicken manure and corn cob biochar at a 4:1 ratio, A2 = Combination of chicken manure and corn cob biochar at a 4:2 ratio, A3 = Combination of chicken manure and corn cob biochar at a 1:1 ratio, A4 = Combination of cattle manure and corn cob biochar at a 4:1 ratio, A5 = Combination of cattle manure and corn cob biochar at a 4:2 ratio, A6 = Combination of cattle manure and corn cob biochar at a 1:1 ratio

Soil amendment plays the role of a remediator of soil contaminants such as pesticide residues, and it can improve the physical, chemical, and biological fertilities in paddy soils. According to Peng et al. (2012), application of soil amendment materials such as organics increases the parameters of soil quality indicators such as soil aggregate, organic C content, total N, available K, CEC; it also reduces bulk density and alkaline pH in soil. Adding farmyard manure and biochar to soil facilitates roots' penetration so that they can absorb available nutrients for better growth. The existence of farmyard manure and biochar in soils streamlines nutrient uptake by rice crops suitable for their requirements. This means biochar helps to increase the efficiency of inorganic fertilizers and grain yields of rice crops (Jones et al. 2012). Research results in south China showed that applying biochar at a dosage of 10 and 40 tons per hectare increased grain yields by about 12-14%, respectively, in soils without applying N fertilizer. Meanwhile, these numbers were 8.8% and 12.1%, respectively, in soil where N fertilizer was applied (Zhang et al. 2010).

The increase in grain yield in paddy soils from Jombang district through the application of farmyard manure combined corn cob biochar was influenced by roots' effectiveness in absorbing nutrients that were translocated into plant tissue and soil characteristics. Soil reacted with a pH level of 6-6.5 and available water during crop growth, and this supported the uptake of nutrients and water

effectively (Figure 5). According to Haynes and Mokolobate (2001), submerged paddy soils can increase the decomposition rate of organic matter and this stimulates an increase in pH in acidic soils. The rise in soil pH occurred due to an increase in negative charges on the adsorption surface that might provide readily essential nutrients for crop uptake.

Figure 5. Change of soil acidity (a) and redox potential (b) in rice rhizosphere, 2015-2016

CONCLUSION

- After remediation of contaminated paddy soils, the lowest concentration of endosulfan residue is achieved when treatment combines cattle manure and corn cob biochar at a ratio of 4:1, especially during the panicle initiation and maturity growth phases. This scenario reduces the concentrations by about 68.1% and 62.8%, respectively, compared with treatment not using soil amendment.
- Application of farmyard manure combined with biochar generally increases the total bacteria and fungi population in soils in the rice crop's rhizosphere. The microbial population tends to be high if composted cattle manure and not chicken manure is used.
- Application of farmyard manure combined with corn cob biochar reduces endosulfan residue in percolation water.
- Combining farmyard manure and corn cob biochar significantly reduces endosulfan residue which is absorbed into rice grains, and its residue concentration is smaller than MRLs (0.1 ppm). The highest reduction of residue was achieved when treatment combined composted cattle manure and corn cob biochar at a ratio of 4:1.
- Besides functioning as a remediator, farmyard manures and corn cob biochar when combined significantly improved crop productivity by as much as 8%–26%.

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